

Copperplate Inscriptions of West Bengal: Finding Find-spots and Locating Localities

for Dr. H. O.
with best
wishes
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ABSTRACT: More than one hundred copperplate and stone inscriptions of the early medieval period record transfer of land within the orbit of historical Bengal. Of these, nineteen plates hail from seventeen provenances located within the present political-administrative boundary of West Bengal. Further, out of these nineteen, one plate records grant of land in the Bogra district of the present Bangladesh. Thus, eighteen copperplates datable between the sixth and twelfth centuries CE are historically connected with the growth and expansion of early medieval rural settlements in West Bengal. The paper is primarily aimed at preparation of a detailed settlement database for an ongoing project on the archaeological study of early medieval settlements of West Bengal.

KEYWORDS: Early medieval, copperplates, provenance, identification, village settlements.

1. INTRODUCTORY

Lionel D. Barnett came across, in the Museum of Perth in Australia, a copperplate inscription accompanying a paper that was in fact the 'copy of a somewhat unsuccessful attempt to translate and annotate the plate' by one 'R. Mitro' of the Asiatic Society, dated '6 December 1854'. The plate was presented to Mr J. Greig after its discovery from the 'Indigo Estate of Mallia by one of Mr James Smith's villagers' (Barnett 1983: 60). One hardly finds any difficulty in understanding that 'R. Mitro' was the noted nineteenth-century art historian-epigraphist Rajendra Lal Mitra and the copperplate in question was the 'Mallia' or 'Vappaghoshavata' plate dated in the ruling year of Jayanāga, a seventh-century ruler of Bengal having his administrative headquarters at Karṇṇasuvārṇṇa. But most significantly, the paper cited by Barnett in his introductory note to the decipherment of the plate is the earliest surviving official record on the discovery of a land grant inscription within the administrative orbit of West Bengal.¹

Since the discovery of Jayanāga's plate till date, a substantial quantum of inscribed charters in copper and stone from different parts of West Bengal and Bangladesh has accumulated. In precise numerical terms, altogether one

hundred and one inscriptions, recording rural land transfer and allied affairs within the geographical orbit of early Bengal, have been published after comprehensive decipherment or preliminary notice. Primarily these inscriptions are drafted in the form of legal documents recording permanent alienation of selective plots/villages – within a given geographic-administrative area – towards individual or institutional benefactions of Brahmanical or Buddhist/Jain affiliation. Apart from their potential in the study of various facets of early-early medieval history of eastern and northern India, these land transfer documents bear vivid testimony to an unprecedented growth and expansion of agriculture-based village settlements in characteristically varying terrains of Bengal.

Out of these epigraphic records, a set of nineteen from seventeen provenances datable between the sixth and twelfth centuries CE are distributed within the present administrative boundary of West Bengal (Fig. 1). As just stated, the source-value of these inscriptions for the study of archaeology of early medieval settlements can hardly be overemphasized. The most vital set of clues embedded in these inscriptions is in the form of a large number of ancient settlements, many of which are still identifiable on ground. Even

FIG. 1. Spatial distribution of copperplate inscriptions in West Bengal.

more crucial is the issue of location of actual inscriptional provenance which in most cases has a close spatial connection with the land alienation programme described in the epigraphic text. A thorough scrutiny of the available records from West Bengal clearly shows that in many instances the epigraphic provenances have remained improperly located² and still larger number of early settlements have either not been identified or have remained perfunctorily known, although the editors of the inscriptions sometimes left invaluable clues to their proper identification (Sanyal 2008). The present essay focuses on the copperplate inscriptions of West Bengal and undertakes a detailed study on the recovery or research of epigraphic provenances and identification of rural settlements recorded in these epigraphs, either in the light of a detailed scrutiny of already existing literature or with the help of fresh field research.

2. GEOCHRONOLOGICAL ATTRIBUTIONS

Arranged in terms of historical chronology of the region, the following is the list of early medieval inscriptions from West Bengal:

1. Malla Sarul plate of the time of Gopacandra,
2. Antla ('Medinipur') plate (no. 1) of the time of Śaśāṅka,
3. Antla ('Medinipur') plate (no. 2) of the time of Śaśāṅka,
4. Panchrol ('Egra') plate of the time of Śaśāṅka,
5. Maliadanga ('Mallia') plate of the time of Jayanāga,
6. Karnasuvarna plate of the time of Dharmapāla,
7. Tulabhita ('Jagajjibanpur') plate of the time of Mahendrapāla,
8. Bangarh plate of the time of Mahīpāla,
9. Jajilpara plate of the time of Gopāla III³,
10. Sibbati ('Rajibpur') plate (no. 1) of the time of Madanapāla,
11. Sibbati ('Rajibpur') plate (no. 2) of the time of Madanapāla,
12. Barrackpur plate of the time of Vijayasena,
13. Naihati plate of the time of Vallālasena,
14. Govindapur plate of the time of Lakṣmaṇasena,
15. Tarpandighi plate of the time of Lakṣmaṇasena,
16. Dighirpar-Bakultala ('Sundarban') plate of the time of Lakṣmaṇasena,
17. Anulia plate of the time of Lakṣmaṇasena,
18. Saktipur plate of the time of Lakṣmaṇasena,
- and 19. Rakshaskhali plate of the time of

Dommanapāla. Thus, altogether there are five copperplates of the post-Gupta and pre-Pāla phase, datable between the sixth and seventh centuries. No record of the intervening eighth century has so far been discovered from the region. Belonging to the Pāla period is again a set of five copperplates datable from the ninth to the twelfth centuries and all coming from the present Malda and Dakshin [South] Dinajpur districts in West Bengal. The rest of the eight copperplates are all dated to the Sena period. All of them belong to the second half of the twelfth century and geographically distributed over a wide area from Tarpandighi in the extreme north (in the South Dinajpur district) to Rakshaskhali in far south (in the South 24 Parganas district).

The plates hail from four broader geographical niches of West Bengal: 1. Different micro regional blocks of the broader coastal uplands in the southwest to the bordering areas of coastal and lateritic (*rarh*) tracts, 2. The wider alluvial terrains to the west of the Hooghly-Bhagirathi basin area, 3. The alluvial uplands along the valley of the middle Damodar, 4. The present Barind tract consisting parts of the Mahananda-Punarbhaha-Chiramati hydrographic systems.

3. PROVENANCES AND IDENTIFICATION OF SETTLEMENTS

If one juxtaposes the spatial and temporal contexts of these inscriptions, a sharp inconsistency in the geochronological pattern of their occurrence will be quite apparent. In spite of this inconsistency, it is not altogether inconvenient to further subdivide the above fourfold spatial patterning into six geographical-geological zones (Fig. 2). This spatial spread clearly indicates the existence of three major and one minor clusters of epigraphic sites, besides the two isolated find-spots in six varying zones. Since the paper primarily concentrates on settlements, it will not be out of place to reconsider the database in terms of location of find-spots within each of the zones noted above.

FIG. 2. Six major geographical zones and nature of distribution of copperplates in each zone.

3.1 Zone I

This zone roughly includes the South Dinajpur and the northern part of the Malda districts. The region is topographically characterized by rolling plains dotted with lakes and marshes. Geomorphologically the area comprises 'fan surfaces' formed by silt and clay; usually areas to the east of the river Kalindri are low-lying plains – a part of the Tal formation. The river Punarbhaba, one of the tributaries of Mahananda, has a meandering course that runs almost across this zone. The alluvial plains along the west bank of the river Ganga borders the zone to the entire western part. Morphostratigraphy of the zone represents two different sediments in the form of 'low altitude fan surface on middle Holocene alluvial fan surface' termed as the *Baikunthapur* surface and the 'alluvial upland on late Pleistocene to early Holocene terraced sediments' known as the *Sijua/Barind* surface (Ghosh and Majumdar 1991). Epigraphic provenances located within this zone are Bangarh, Sibbati, Tarpandighi, Jajilpada, and Tulabhita.

3.1.1 Bangarh Plate of the Time of Mahīpāla I

The plate was discovered in the late nineteenth century from the site of Bangarh in the village of Rajibpur in the Gangarampur Police Station of South Dinajpur district. The plate was edited twice by F. Keilhorn (Keilhorn 1892) and R. D. Banerji (Banerji 1982a). Banerji reports that '[t]he grant was discovered among ruins called Bān rājā's garh or Bangarh, in the Dinajpur district of the Presidency of Bengal, during the latter decades of the nineteenth century' (Banerji 1982a: 324).

The plate is dated in the thirty-third ruling year of Mahīpāla I around *c.* late tenth or early eleventh century CE and was issued from the administrative headquarters of Vilāsapura, recording grant of land in the 'Kurāṭa pallikā with the exception of Cūta pallikā with low ground, in the Gokalikā *maṇḍala* of the Koṭivarṣa *viṣaya* in the Puṇḍravaraddhana *bhukti*' (Banerji 1982a: 330). No detailed boundary of the granted land

is specified in the epigraph. The only other geographical data is provided by the name of a village called Poṣālī from where hailed the artisan named Mahīdhara. It has not so far been possible to identify either the granted locality of Kurāṭa *pallikā* or Poṣālī.

3.1.2 Sibbati ('Rajibpur') Plates of the Time of Madanapāla

'These two plates were discovered by one Ashok Nandi, while tilling land, in the Shibbari village near Rajibpur in the Gangarampur Police Station of the [then] West Dinajpur district' – reports the editor of the plates (translated after Mukherjee 1990-91: 27). An interview with Ashok Nandi later revealed that a tribal woman chanced upon the plates while collecting earth from the mound in the month of October of 2009. Actually Sibbati/Sibbari is a separate sector of the same Rajibpur village, forming one of the major structural sites in the larger Bangarh cluster of sites.

The plates are dated in the second and twenty-second/thirty-second ruling years of the Pāla king Madanapāla and may thus be dated to *c.* middle or early second half of twelfth century CE. Both the plates were issued from the royal headquarters located at Rāmāvati. The first plate of year two records the donation of land at the Buddhavaḍā *grāma* in Halāvartta *maṇḍala* of Koṭivarṣa *viṣaya* in Puṇḍravaraddhana *bhukti* to a Brāhmaṇa named Muraripu Rāta, while the second plate records donation of land after about two-three decades to one Mahādeva Rāta, son of Muraripu within the same village Budhavaḍā though by then it came to be known as a *pallī* attached to the Koṣṭhāgāra of Devikoṭa in the same administrative area. No detailed boundary of the village Budhavaḍā is specified in either of the plates, though the brief narrative provided in the second plate in connection with the location of the village is quite interesting. It suggests that the village is 'situated at a fragment of land to the south of the granary of Devikoṭa' (translated after Mukherjee 1990-91: 34). Two neighbouring localities called Varaṇḍa *pallī* at-

tached to Vaṅgaḍī and Viduṣa *ballī* (i.e. *pallī*) are mentioned in the inscription.

One may add here that a recent corroborative study of the epigraphic contents of the second Rajibpur plate with available archaeological data from the region has led one to identify beyond any doubt the village of Budhura (now more popular as Raghampur), in the Tapan Police Station at its border with that of Gangarampur, with early medieval Budhavaḍā (Sanyal: forthcoming). It is encouraging to find that the village still lies at a fragment of land towards east to the due south of the excavated segment of Bangarh that yielded the brick-built public granaries of the Pāla period excavated by K. G. Goswami in the first half of the preceding century (Goswami 1948). Although the name Budhura has come to be replaced by its present name Raghampur, local oral history of the territory still recognizes its earlier social identity as a seat of learned Brāhmaṇas (the actual meaning of the term Budhavaḍā also signifying the same, i.e. *Budha* = learned/scholarly, *Vaḍā* = sector of a village, evidently in the sense of modern Bengali *para* or *palli*).

3.1.3 *Tarpandighi Plate of the Time of Lakṣmaṇasena*

The plate was first brought to the public notice by E. V. Westmacott as part of his report of 'tours' in north Bengal (Westmacott 1875) and was later edited twice by R. D. Banerji (Banerji 1982c: 6-10) and N. G. Majumdar (Majumdar 1929: 99-105). The plate was discovered in course of re-excavating an old tank during the scarcity of 1873-74, to the north of Tarpandighi, Tarpandighi or Tapandighi, which is the largest tank in the district of Dinajpur, about 6 miles to the south of Gangarampur Police Station in the Balurghat subdivision... . Under circumstances, which are not recorded, the plate after its discovery came to the possession of Sir William Le Fleming Robinson, Bart, of Gloucestershire, England, whose nephew Sir Ernest Robinson brought it to Calcutta and sold it to the Vangiya-Sahitya Parishat (Majumdar 1929: 99).

Dated in the second year of the reign of Lakṣmaṇasena, the Tarpandighi grant speaks of donation at the Velahiṣṭī *grāma* in Varendrī in the Pauṇḍravarddhana *bhukti* within the following boundary:

To the east, the eastern boundary wall of (one) āḍhavāpa of rent-free plain land (?) belonging to the deity of Buddhist monastery; to the south, the Nichadahāra tank (or 'the tank belonging to Nichadahāra'); to the west, the Nandiharipā-kuṇḍā (or 'the tank belonging to Nandiharipā'); to the north, Mollāna-khāḍi (or 'the ditch belonging to Mollāna...).

Earlier epigraphists dealing in the copperplate failed to identify the donated village with any existing village in north Bengal. However, it is tempting to identify, though tentatively, the Velahiṣṭī of the Tarpandighi grant with the present village named Belasthali, not far from the provenance of the plate, to the east of Bangarh and northeast of Tapan in the Gangarampur Police Station of the district of South Dinajpur. Belasthali is reported to have possessed 'numerous bronzes and stone images' of the early medieval period besides pottery and structures of later periods (Panja 2002: 243). It may also be rewarding to inquire in terms of an intensive field survey, if the area around the village possesses any trace of a structural ruin/associated archaeological material that might be taken as a monastic mound or part/s thereof. In that case, it will be a solid corroboration of the epigraphic statement that lands belonging to the organization of a Buddhist monastery formed one of the boundaries of the granted land.

3.1.4 *Jajilpara Plate of the Time of Gopāla III*

While editing the inscription, P. N. Misra and R. C. Majumdar recorded that

[t]he copperplate which bears this inscription was in possession of a cultivator of Jajilpara, a village within police station Gazole and near the border of Malda and Dinajpur districts. He found it while digging the founda-

tions of his mud-walled house, and kept it as an object of curiosity. Mr K. C. Burman... presented it to the Malda Museum, where it is being preserved at present (Misra and Majumdar 1951: 137).

The plate was issued from Vaṭa-Parvatikā in the sixth regnal year of Gopāla III in *c.* early or middle of the eleventh century CE and it records grant of land in the Kāṣṭhāgṛha and Mahārāja *pallī* of the Ānandapura *agrahāra* 'along with the prospective Dvārikadāna' in the Kuddālakhāta *viṣaya* of the Puṇḍravarddhana *bhukti*. The inscription further provides that the donee resided in the village named Siha and he originally hailed from Muktvastu *grāma*. No details of the boundary of the granted land is supplied in the charter. The editors add, as usual, the following note on the present locations of identifiable settlements mentioned in the inscription:

There is a village named 'Siha' or 'Sihole' on the Gazole-Dinajpur Road, in the Bansihari Police Station, Dinajpur district. At present it is a very small hamlet, but according to the local tradition it was formerly a big village inhabited by a large number of learned Brāhmaṇas. Even now, some Varendra Brāhmaṇas reside in the village called Mahagrām, about less than a mile from this village. It is situated on the south-eastern bank of the Tangan river and, as a result of erosion of that river; foundations of many brick-built houses have been exposed to view. Its distance from the find-place of the present copperplate is about 7 or 8 miles. It is probable that the site of this village represents the old 'Siha' village. It may be mentioned here that Mr J. C. Ghosh had suggested the identification of 'Siha' with a village named Sahagrām within police station Pārbatipur, in Dinajpur district, on the basis of similarity of names only. As regards Muktvastu, Mr J. C. Ghosh has shown from several epigraphic records that it was situated in Varendra, and was an ancient place of residence of certain Brāhmaṇa families of

Kāśyapa gotra to whom many kings of old had made gifts of land (Misra and Majumdar 1951: 139).

3.1.5 *Tulabhita* ('Jagjivanpur') Plate of the Time of Mahendrapāla

The unusually large copperplate with a distinctly carved circular seal bearing the name *Mahendrapāladeva* dated in the middle of the ninth century was first identified as an inscribed record of a Pāla king named Mahendrapāla by Sudhir Kumar Chakravarty in a local magazine of Malda, known as *Gangabridi Malda* and was then brought to the notice of the wider academic circle by Amitabha Bhattacharya (Bhattacharya 1987) and Gouriswar Bhattacharya (Bhattacharya 1988, 1997-99). The plate has since been edited or noted by several authorities (Bhattacharya 1992a, 1994, 2000: 407-10, 431-8, 441-54; Bhattacharya 2007, Gupta 1989, 1991, Mukherjee 1997, Mukherjee 1989, 1992, 1997-98a; Ramesh and Iyer 1992). The *Tulabhita* copperplate, undoubtedly the most significant epigraphic discovery bearing on the polity of eastern India in the twentieth century,

was discovered in the village of Jagajjivanpur (Mauza Jagajjivanpur, PS Habibpur, Dist. Malda) on 13.3.87, while a certain Jagadish Chandra Gayen was digging the foundation of a mound named *Tulabhita* (or *Salaidanga*) situated in the said village. The copperplate was collected by the Officer-in-charge of Habibpur PS soon after, and was later on handed over to Sri Sadhan Chandra Dev, Asst. Curator of Malda Museum, where it is now being preserved (Ramesh and Iyer 1992: 6).

The most significant aspect of the inscription has of course been the fact that it recorded the name of the Pāla king Mahendrapāla whose donative records were long known to the historians and epigraphists but were mistaken as those of a Pratihāra ruler of the same name (Bhattacharya 1988).

The *Tulabhita* plate records the grant of some land in a 'locality marked with/abounding

in water bodies' (*udraṅga*)⁴ called Nandadīrghikā in the Kuddālakḥātaka *viṣaya* within the Puṇḍravarddhana province to a Buddhist monastery-belonging to the Avaivarttika subsect of the Mahāyāna school-named after the same tank (i.e. Nandadīrghikā) in the same locality. It was issued in the seventh year of Mahendrapāla's reign. Subsequent digging at the provenance has provided clinching evidence, in the form of a brick-built Buddhist monastery named Nandadīrghikā *viḥarā*, towards authenticity of the statement (Roy 2002). The detailed boundaries of the granted land have also been delineated in the epigraph:

There the half stream of the river *Taṅgila* marks the boundary on the east and (partly) on the south too, which is (further) demarcated by the half stream of *Kubja-ghaṭikā*, *Kāśiggara-bandhāka*, in the middle, stretching up to the eastern boundary of *Nārāyana-vāsa*. The western boundary is marked by *Golayi nirjjhara*, the low land (*avakhāta*) of *Ajagara-vāsaka* (python habitat), termite mound, *āsvattha* tree (the holy fig tree, *Ficus Religiosa*), the western bank (*paścima pāṭa*) of *Svalpanandādhāra*, the *vilva* tree (*Aegle Marmelos*, bel) west of *Bijjaga-bandh*, the *āmalaki* tree (*Emblic Myrobalam*) six reeds away (*ṣaṇ=ṇal = āntara*). Next, the northern boundary consists of the east-facing northern water-holes, and (the area) from *Nandasurāli* on the south up to the half stream of (the river) *Taṅgila* (Bhattacharya 2007: 76).⁵

S. C. Mukherjee adds the following note regarding identification of place names recorded in the epigraph:

1. Kuddālakḥāta (°khātaka)-Kuddālakḥāta as a *viṣaya* has been mentioned in the Jajilpada C. P. grant of Gopāla II or III (962 A.D.). In the present record this appellation appears both as a place-name and as the name of a *viṣaya*... 3. Taṅgila river-It is tempting to identify this river with modern Tāngan, which as a tributary of the Māthā-

bhāṅgā originates from the base of the Himalayas and traverses districts of Jalpaiguri, West Dinajpur and Malda. The Mahānandā entering Malda district near Kusidha (Purnea border) and flowing past towns of Malda and Aiho, enter Rajshahi district in Bangladesh in south-east. 4. Nandadīrghikā-The Lake may be identified with modern Nandgarh or Nādgārh Bill (Nandadīrghī), not far away from the mound of Tulābhītā (to the south) of Jagajjivanpur. 5. Kāśiggara-bandhaka-The embankment of Kāśiggara was probably situated near modern Kāsi Dīghi, lying to the north of Nandadīghi (Mukherjee 1997-98a: 60-1).

3.2 Zone II

This zone, located along the right bank of the Ganga, is actually an extension of the Ganga-Brahmaputra Delta and is mostly formed by alluvial depositions. Geomorphologically, the zone is characterized mainly by Deltaic plains bordering the alluvial uplands to the west. The main channels that pass across this zone are those of the Ganga, the Bhagirathi, the Mayurakshi, the Jalangi, and the Kopai. Sparse distribution of backwaters and oxbow lakes characterizes the zone in general. Morphostratigraphically the area represents a blend of land surfaces of the *Sijua* formation and the 'upper mature deltaic plains on middle holocene estuarine sediments of the *Dumdum* surface'. Inscriptional sites of the zone include Karnasuvarna, Maliadanga, Saktipur, and Naihati.

3.2.1 Karnasuvarna ('Murshidabad') Plate of the time of Dharmapāla

The existence of a 'Murshidabad copperplate' of the reign of Dharmapāla was first noticed by S. C. Mukherjee who only noted that the plate hailed from 'a place in the district of Murshidabad' (Mukherjee 1992: 171). Subsequently, Gouriswar Bhattacharya reported more precisely that the plate, now preserved in the Indian Museum at Kolkata (Accession no. 90/131), was actually acquired from a villager of

Murshidabad, who reportedly collected it from a villager living around the noted archaeological site of Karnasuvarna in the Kansona region of the same district on the Bhagirathi in 1990 (Bhattacharya 1994, 2000: 441-2; see also Khan 2007: 11).

Suresh Chandra Bhattacharya has recently edited the reverse of the plate and this shows that the plate must have originally hailed from north Bengal, since the grant records land donation in favour of the noted Somapura *Mahāvihāra* built under the patronage of Dharmapāla at Paharpur in Bangladesh (Bhattacharya 2008).

3.2.2 Maliadanga ('Mallia') Plate of the Time of Jayanāga

The provenance of this charter has remained improperly recorded for a long time. The editor of the plate reports (Barnett 1983: 60) that

The record belongs to the Museum of Perth ... It was presented to the Museum some time ago by Mr. J. Greig of Calcutta. The Museum possesses a paper signed by him and containing a copy of a somewhat unsuccessful attempt to translate and annotate the plate, which bears the subscription: "R. Mittro, Asiatic Society, 6th December 1854," and to which Mr. Greig has prefixed the note "Translation of a Copper Plate found in the Indigo Estate of Mallia by one of Mr. James Smith's villagers, and presented to me by that gentleman in January 1855.

As Barnett was unable to locate Mallia, he 'judged it advisable to designate the charter by the name of the village granted in it.' B. M. Morrison reported that the plate was found 'at the indigo estate of Mr James Smith at Malliā, about 30 mile south of Burdwan in 1855' (Morrison 1970: 160), although he did not cite any reference in justification of its association with the Bardhaman district. Ayoub Khan records the provenance of the plate, in his most recent and exhaustive study on the provenances of Bengal copperplates, as 'Old Nadia' depending evidently on Barnett's identification of the

granted village with Ghoshpara located in the Nadia district (Khan 2007: 8).

The only clue in locating the exact find-spot of the record is the mention of a administrative subdivision (*viṣaya*) named Audumvarika unanimously taken to have been located in the Murshidabad (Banerji 1983) or the 'Birbhum-Murshidabad' region (Sircar 1985: 113). It is quite surprising that neither Burnett nor any of the subsequent epigraphists or historians dealing in the record paid attention to the fact that a village called Maliadanga (24°18'58" N, 88°03'02") still exists in the Sagardighi Police Station of the district of Murshidabad. Not only the local oral history of the region bears vivid testimony to the once existing Indigo estate at the village, but most significantly the entire habitation of the modern village stands atop a large dissected mound strewn with pottery and other habitation remains. Thus, one may conveniently identify the village 'Mallia' of Burnett with present Maliadanga, the actual provenance of the copperplate.

The charter was issued from Karnasuvarna, identified with the modern Jadupur (former Chiruti) village of Murshidabad (Das 1968, 1992), by Śrī-Jayanāga and recorded the grant of a village named Vappaghoṣavāta *grāma* in the Audumvarika *viṣaya*. A number of rural localities and natural landmarks are mentioned in the grant portion of the inscription in connection with the boundary specifications:

The signs of the boundary therein are: on the west, the boundary of the grant belonging to the Brahmans of the Kuṭkuṭa *grāma*; on the north, the river-bed; on the east the same river-bed; issuing thence and running along the western boundary of Amalapautika-*grāma*, (the boundary) is the Sarshapayānaka; it is limited by the same [boundary], as far as Bhaṭṭa Unmilana-svāmin's grant; from the south thereof, (the boundary), turning along further by the same boundary to the north, proceeds as far as the boundary of Bharanī-svāmin's grant, thence in a straight line enters the pond of Vakhata Sūmālikā on

the boundary of Bhaṭṭa Unmilana-svāmin's grant; and goes as far as the same boundary of Brāhmaṇas of Kuṭkuṭa-grāma (Burnett 1983: 63).

There has been considerable debate between L. D. Burnett and R. D. Banerji, the two editors of the plate, regarding identification of the localities mentioned in the record. Burnett suggests that

The names of places mentioned, besides Karṇasuvarṇaka, are the Audumbarika viṣaya; the villages of Vappaghoshavāta, the Kuṭkuṭa-grāma, and Amalapautika-grāma; Gaṅginikā, Literally "river", which here is perhaps used as a proper name; the Sarshapa-yānaka or "mustard channel"; and the pool of Vakhata-Sūmālikā... I am indebted to Mr. S. K. Chatterji... for the following observation. The Gaṅginikā seems to be the river Jalāṅgī, a branch of the Ganges or Padma which unites with the Bhagirathi near Nadiya, the classical Navadvīpa. In the Survey map of the Nadia District, Bagwan is a village in the Meharpur subdivision, and close to it, on the two sides of the Jalāṅgī, are the villages of Badagāchī ("Burgachee") and Ānduliyā ("Andooleea"), as stated by Bharatachandra. It seems likely that this river Jalāṅgī, is the Gaṅginikā of the present record. North of Bagwan, at some distance from the Jalāṅgī, is an important village named Gaṅganī, which may possibly preserve the name of the Gaṅginikā... But it may be noted that Vappaghoshavāta (vappa is the Bengali *bāp*, "father", and *ghoshavāta* "dwelling of herdsmen") would be a likely village-name in Southern Murshidabad and Nadia, where there was much cattle breeding. A Ghoshpādā exists in the south, on the Bhāgīrathi, and is well known as the home of the founder of the Kartābhajā sect... (Burnett 1983: 64).

R. D. Banerji, on the other hand, argues, quite justifiably, that

The *vishaya* of Udumbara mentioned... is better known than it is supposed... Audumbara

existed as the name of a division of Bengal and elsewhere in India up to at least the end of the sixteenth century... Among the *Mahalls* mentioned as being included in the Sarkar Audumbar in the Ā'in there are at least two which bear the same name in early British Revenue Papers; e.g., Ākmahal and Kunwarpartab... Kunwarpartab is really Kumārapratāpe, and bears this name even now. It is a *paraganah* in the northern part of the Murshidabad district. There cannot be any doubt therefore that portions of Sarkar Audumbar lay to the south of the Ganges and west of the Bhāgīrathi... [t]here cannot be any reason to suppose that the name of the *Vishaya* in Jayanāga's grant, which is also the same, was situated in the Delta of Bengal near modern Ranaghat, where no such Revenue Division is proved to have existed. The term Gaṅginikā is the diminutive of Gaṅgini. Gani and Gaṅgina are common terms in western Bengal for a dried up riverbed or a small river. The name Gaṅginika was equally common in Northern Bengal (Banerji 1983: 286-7).

Considering the spatial limits of the Audumbarika *viṣaya* in the 'Birbhum-Murshidabad' region, it will be tempting to identify Kutigram and Ambha in the contiguous Rampurhat Police Station of the Birbhum district with Kuṭkuṭa *grāma* and Amalapautika *grāma* respectively. Furthermore, if the boundary specification of the granted village is juxtaposed against the location of these two identifiable villages, it will be a distinct possibility that the name Vappaghoshavāta exists in the name of the village Bhabki, located just between the two above-mentioned villages. The proposition, however, demands confirmation in the light of a detailed exploratory survey of the region.

3.2.3 Saktipur Plate of the Time of Lakṣmaṇasena

D. C. Ganguly first reported the copperplate with the following note on the circumstances under which it was discovered:

The new copper-plate was lying in the house of Late Mr. Siva Chandra Chatterjee, in the village of Saktipur, in the Sadar-Subdivision of the Murshidabad District, Bengal, where it is said to have been worshipped for a long time by a widow, now dead. It is now lying in the Museum of the Bangiya Sahitya Parishat (Ganguly 1984: 211).

Issued in the fourth regnal year of Lakṣmaṇasena, the charter bespeaks land donation in parts of the Nimā *pātaka*, Vārahakoṇā, Vāllihitā, Vījahārapura and Dāmaravadā *pātakas* in Kumārapura *caturaka* in Madhugiri *maṇḍala* attached to Kumbhīnagara in Dakṣiṇa *vīthī* in Uttara Rādha in Kaṅkagrāma *bhukti* having their boundaries delineated in the following manner (Ganguly 1984: 213).

The lands comprising Vārahakoṇā, Vāllihitā, Rāghavahaṭṭa and part of Nimā were contiguous, and were bounded in the east by the extensive lands of Mālikuṇḍā along with Aparājoli; in the south by Bhāgaḍikhaṇḍa-kshetra, in the west by the cow-track of Achchhamā and in the north by the Mora river. The two *pātakas* of Vījahārapura and Dāmaravadā which were off from the above lands, were again contiguous. They were bounded on the east by Chākaliyājoli; on the south by Vipravarddjolī, on the west by Lāṅgalājoli and on the north by the cow-track of Parajāna.

A detailed note on the probable locations of identifiable settlements was also provided by Ganguly, though no subsequent archaeological study has so far been made towards extension of the data provided by him. Thus, according to Ganguly,

The place Kaṅkagrāma from which the *bhukti* took its name can be identified which Kāṅkjol (24°48' N, 87°48' E) just beyond the northern limits of the Murshidabad and Birbhum Districts of Bengal. Cunningham calls it 'an old town, which was once the headquarters of an extensive province, including the whole of the present district of

Rājmaḥal and a large tract of country which is now on the east of the Ganges, but which in former days was on its west bank.' Its situation 'on a jutting point of the old high bank of the Ganges' must have given it a strategic importance. According to Cunningham, 'the province in which it is situated was called Rādha by the Hindus.' Besides the antiquities noticed by Cunningham, there are other important antiquities at Kendua in the neighbourhood of Kāṅkjol, which indicate that the place was of considerable importance in the pre-Muhammadan period. There can therefore be little doubt about the proposed identification.

The name of the ancient Madhugiri-*maṇḍala* may be recognised in the present Mahuagadhi, an isolated hill, in Santal Parganas rising to a height of 1,657 feet above sea level and situated about 22 miles to the south-west of Kankjol and 20 miles north-west of Kumhira.—Ed.]

Of the other localities mentioned in the inscription, Kumbhīnagara may be identified with the modern Kumhira, in the Rampurhat P.S. of the Birbhum District. The river Mora is the modern Mor (also known as Mayurakshi) which flows through the Birbhum District. Kumārapura still retains its ancient name and is situated in P.S. Maureswar about 3½ miles north of the Mor. Vārahakoṇā is the modern Barkunda in P. S. Suri, about ½ a mile north of the Mor and 1½ mile from the Sainthia railway station of the E. R. Loop line. The words *koṇā* and *kuṇḍā* are changeable according to the usage in the Birbhum District. The modern village of Baharpur in the Labpur P.S. of Birbhum District probably represents the ancient Vījahārapura. Mr. N. K. Bhattasali identifies Nimā and Vāllihitā with the modern villages of Nimā and Bāluti in P.S. Maureswar, on the north bank of the Mor, 4 miles north-east from Sainthiā and 5½ miles west of Kumārapur. He also identifies Achchhamā with the modern village of Ammo in P.S. Suri, ½ a mile north of Sainthiā and Parajāna with that of Pailijana, a village

on both sides of the Mor, in P.S. Labpur and P.S. Maureswar, about 5 miles north-west of Baharpur. The villages of Barkunda, Nima and Baluti are now on the north bank of the Mor when the inscription tells us that they were to the south of this river. This shows that the Mor, which is a restless river constantly shifting its sandy bed, has since changed its course. The dried-up bed of the modern Kana River, passing north of Nimā and Bāluti, was most probably the ancient course of the Mor during the Sena period. [Bārkonā would be a better equivalent of Vārahakoṇā and a well-known ancient locality exists under this name close to Pānchthupi in the Kāndi Subdivision of Murshidābād. In the vicinity are also to be found Nimā and Bāluti, and the river Mor drags on its course at some distance to the south.

3.2.4 *Naihati Plate of the Time of Vallālasena*

The copperplate was discovered from the village Naihati in the borderland of the districts of Bardhaman and Murshidabad within the jurisdiction of the former in the Katwa Police Station and was deciphered by a number of scholars like T. C. Ray, B. L. Goswami, A. K. Maitreya, and R. G. Basak in some noted Bengali periodicals (see Majumdar 1929: 68 for all references) before it was edited with roman transliteration by R. D. Banerji (Banerji 1982b) and then by N. G. Majumdar (Majumdar 1929: 68-80). Banerji gives an appreciably vivid account of the circumstances under which the plate was discovered:

The plate on which this grant is incised was discovered by some coolies, while digging some waste land, between the villages of Naihati and Sitahati in the Katwa subdivision of the Burdwan district of Bengal, belonging to Babu Baidyanath Chatterji, Zamindar of Sitahati, in January 1911. The piece of waste land on which the grant was discovered is called by the local people *Nai Rajar Bhita*, "The ruins of Nai Raja's Pal-

ace". A copper cup, "tamrakunda", a vessel still in common use for divine worship in Bengal, was discovered at the same time. Subsequent excavations at the same place yielded some more utensils of worship (Banerji 1982b: 156).

Majumdar also offers a similar account about the provenance as he writes that the inscription was discovered 'by a number of labourers while repairing a road in the village of Naihati' (Majumdar 1929: 68)

It is quite significant to note Banerji's concerns in delineating in substantial details the artefacts found from the location of occurrence of the copperplate, evidently showing his keen interest on the archaeological characters of the provenance called *Nai Rajar Garh* which, according to his estimates was an early medieval temple site. It may not be out of place to cite Banerji's descriptive account of the discoveries from the site followed by his own observation on the nature of the site. Thus, Banerji enlists, among notable archaeological objects,

(1) A copper censer on two legs, one of which is peculiarly carved. Such censers are very often represented on the pedestals of images of the Pāla period (800-1200 A.D.). This form is no longer used in Bengal. Dr. J. Ph. Vogel, when Officiating Director General of Archaeology, found similar utensils for *pūjā*, made of brass, in the Tirumalavadi Temple of Vaidyanātha, Trichinopoly district, Madras. The censer had a movable cover, which has now disappeared and of which the hinge only remains. It measures 7" in length and $4\frac{3}{4}$ " in height.

(2-5) Four small stands of cups, most probably intended to hold *pāni-sankhas*, or conch-shells. No. 2 measures $2\frac{1}{4}$ " height, and the diameter of the top is $1\frac{1}{2}$ ", No. 3 measures $2\frac{1}{16}$ " in height, and the diameter of the top is $1\frac{1}{8}$ ". No. 4 measures 2" in height, and the diameter of top is $\frac{1}{16}$ ". No. 5 measures $1\frac{1}{2}$ " in height, and the diameter of the top is $1\frac{1}{4}$ ".

(6-8) One elaborately carved and two

plainly carved small conch-shells, used during *pūjā*. They are called *pāni-śankhas* and are not used for blowing. They are filled with water, and waved before the deity at the time of *Ārātrikā* [adoration].

(9-12) Four irregular pieces of oxidized zinc.

The nature of the finds indicates that the piece of waste land where the grant and the other objects were discovered is the site of an ancient temple. Local people say that some images made of gold, or covered with gold leaf, were found at the same place. Mr. Tarak Chandra Roy, M.A., when Sub-divisional Officer of Katwa, interrogated the agent of the Zamindar of Sitahati, who denied all knowledge of them. Subsequent

inquires did not lead to the discovery of any such images, and Mr. Ray is inclined to regard the rumours as baseless (Banerji 1982b: 158-9).

The Naihati inscription is dated in the eleventh ruling year of the reign of Vallālasena, son and successor of Vijayasena. The copperplate, issued from Vikramapura, is dated to *c.* second half of twelfth century CE and it records the grant of a village named Vāllahit̥hā in the Uttara Rāḍha *maṇḍala* within the Svalpa-dakṣiṇa *vīthī* of the Varddhamāna *bhukti*. The inscription provides a detailed and complicated account of the spatial boundaries of the granted village with its contiguous and/or neighbouring rural localities. Thus, the village Vāllahit̥hā

FIG. 3. Identified localities mentioned in the Naihati copperplate (after Chattopadhyaya 1990).

was situated to the north of the river Siṅgaṭiā, which lay to the north of the *Śāsana* of Khāṇḍayillā, to the north west of the river Siṅgaṭiā, which lay to the north of the *Śāsana* of Nāḍichā, to the west of the river Siṅgaṭiā, which lay to the west of the *Śāsana* of Āmvayillā, to the south of the southern boundary-wall (*Sīmāli*) of Kuḍumvamā, to the south of the boundary-wall on the west of Kuḍumvamā which runs to the west (*Paśchima-gati*), to the west of the southern cattle track (*gopatha*) on the south of the Āuhāgaḍḍiā, to the south of the boundary-wall which issues from the northern cattle track of Āuhāgaḍḍiā, runs to the west and reaches to the southern boundary-wall of the Surakoṅgaḍḍiā, to the east of the eastern boundary-wall of Nāḍḍinā, to the east of half of the cattle track to the east of the *Śāsana* of Jalasoṭhī, and to the east of half of the cattle track to the east of the *Śāsana* of Molāḍandī (which runs) up to the (river of) Siṅgaṭiā (Banerji 1982b: 158).

The boundary specification clearly shows the existence of as many as nine other rural settlements – besides cattle tracks and a river – apart from the village granted through issuance of the plate. At least five of these villages, viz. Khāṇḍayillā, Nāḍichā, Āmvayillā, Jalasoṭhī, and Molāḍandī, had already been converted to rent-free *śāsana* category settlements, as the description of the boundaries indicates. N. G. Majumdar followed the identifications offered by T. C. Ray:

Besides Vāllahiṭṭhā, the village that was given away, the copper-plate mentions a number of other villages viz. Jalasoṭhī, Khāṇḍayillā, Āmvayillā, and Molāḍandī, which formed its different boundaries. They have been identified by Mr. Tarak Chandra Ray, respectively with modern Bālutiyā, Jalasoṭhī, Khāruliā, Ambalgrām, and Murundī. The present situation of the identified villages is as follows, according to Mr. Ray: Bālutiyā is about 6 miles to the west of

Naiḥātī (the find place of the copper-plate), on the northern boundary of the Burdwan District. To its north is Jalasoṭhī, which is now included in the Murshidabad district. To its south is Khāruliā, to the east and south of which is Ambalgrām. To its west is Murundī. As regards the river Siṅgaṭiā mentioned in the record, Mr. Ray observes that there is at present only a canal to the south and east of the village of Balutiya. This might be the river Siṅgaṭiā although it is not called by that name (Majumdar 1929: 71).

Recently B. D. Chattopadhyaya has precisely demarcated the present locations of identifiable villages (Chattopadhyaya 1990: map facing p. 40) mentioned in the Naihati plate on the current map of the region (Fig. 3). It is quite curious to note that early medieval Jalasoṭhī was located, during the time of the grant, at a point lying to the southwest of the granted village of Vāllahiṭṭhā. Now, the present village of Jalsuti in the Murshidabad district at its border with Bardhaman is located to the northwest of Balutia, identifiable with Vāllahiṭṭhā and due north of Murundi, identifiable with Molāḍandī. This unimpeachably demonstrates the extent to which rural settlements can be spatially fluid with changing spatio-temporal contexts.

3.3 Zone III

The site of Malla Sarul is located on the west bank of the Damodar with the Bhagirathi-Hooghly flowing to the east in perpendicular alignment. Geomorphologically it shows the structural characteristics of the lower Pleistocene to early Holocene terraced sediments of the *Sijua* surface.

3.3.1 Malla Sarul Plate of the Time of Gopacandra

The copperplate was 'discovered in 1929 by Dr Sureshwar Roy in course of re-excavation of an old tank adjoining his house' in the village of Malla Sarul in the present Galsi Police Station of the district of Bardhaman and 'was subse-

FIG. 4. Distribution of identifiable villages recorded in the Malla Sarul plate.

quently presented by him to the Vangīya Sahitya Parishat of Calcutta' (Majumdar 1940: 155).

The plate is dated to the first half of the sixth century. It was issued from the *adikarāna* of the Vakkattaka *vīthī* by Vijayasena in the thirty-third regnal year of his overlord Gopacandra (Majumdar 1940: 156, Mukherjee 1958: 31-8, Chhabra 1958). It records grant of land in the Vettragarttā *grāma* in Vakkattaka *vīthī* in Varddhamāna *bhukti*. The granted rural locality 'was bounded on the east and south by Godha *grāma*, on the north by the Vaṭavallaka *agrahāra* and on the west in part by Āmrāgarttikā.' Besides, a number of rural localities of different categories and their land-holding representatives, figuring in the court at Vakkattaka during the transfer of land, are mentioned in the inscription. The names of the eleven rural localities, apart from Vettragarttā *grāma*, are Godha *grāma*, Ardhakaraka *agrahāra*, Vaṭavallaka *agrahāra*, Koḍḍavira *agrahāra* and Kapistha-*vāṭaka* *agrahāra*, besides Nirvṛta *vāṭaka*, Śālmali *vāṭaka*, Madhu *vāṭaka*, Āmrāgarttikā, Khaṇḍajōṭikā and Vindhyaपुरी. It is interesting to note in the above list a sharp hierarchic arrangement of rural settlements, possibly in accordance with their genesis as a village per se. Thus, one comes across four broader categories:

(a) Settlements styled as *grāma* or 'village' per se. (b) Settlements at least parts of which were converted to into *agrahāra* ('rent-free land'). (c) Settlements termed as *vāṭaka*, etymologically meaning 'the site of a house' but derived at the root from *vāṭa*, meaning 'an enclosure of a (low-caste) village consisting of boundary trees [especially *vāṭa*, i.e. Indian Banyan or *Ficus indica*]; *vāṭaka* should then be better interpreted as a [sub-caste] hamlet with its boundary demarcated with [Banyan] trees (for details see, Monier-Williams 2002: 939). (d) Localities named without any terminological suffix. A further scrutiny is likely to reveal even a more interesting representation. A resident (named Dhanasvamī) of Kapistha-*vāṭaka* figures in the list of official representatives of

the *vīthyadhikarāna* as an *Agrahāriṇa*, automatically suggesting that the locality contained some *agrahāra* lands and therefore formed, at least partially an *agrahāra*. At the same time the settlement retained, as part of its name, the identity of a *vāṭaka*. Does this indicate that Kapistha *vāṭaka*, during the transfer of land at Vettragarttā, was witnessing a transition from a *vāṭaka* to an *agrahāra*?

N. G. Majumdar added the following note on the issue of identification of places mentioned in the inscription:

Most of [the localities] appear to have been situated in neighbourhood of Vettragarttā within Vakkattaka *vīthī*, a part of which was granted to the donee. Vettragarttā itself cannot be located with certainty. But Gōdhāgrāma may be identical with Gōhagrām on the Damodar, to the south-east of Mallasārul where the plate has been found. Amrāgarttikā may be modern Āmbahulā (also called *Śimāsīmī*), to the south of Mallasārul. Khaṇḍajōṭikā is perhaps Khandajuli between Mallasārul and Gōhagrām, while Śālmali may be Mallasārul itself. The name of the *vīthī* Vakkattaka seems to have survived in Baktā, a place immediately to the east of Gōhagrām (Majumdar 1940: 157).

Thus, the editor of the plate was successful in identifying as many as six localities mentioned in the epigraph and two of these – one to the east and south (i.e. Godha *grāma*) and other to the west (i.e. Āmrāgarttikā) – formed immediate boundaries of the granted village. Apart from the already identified localities, an intensive exploration in the area has recently revealed that four other settlements recorded in the grant can also be satisfactorily identified in and around the provenance of the plate. Thus, Koḍḍavira should be identified with Kaitara. Kapistha is undoubtedly Kaspur, Nirvṛta may be identical with modern Nabakhanda and Vindhyaपुरी is modern Bandutia. So, we have ten out of the thirteen localities mentioned in the inscription identified with their modern counterparts. Geographically, these identified settle-

ments are located, to the northern and eastern alluvial tracts of the river Damodar, roughly between 23°15'30"-23°19'28" N and 87°35'14"-87°39'26" E (Fig. 4). The three localities that remain unidentified are Vaṭavallaka *agrahāra*, Madhu *vāṭaka* and most significantly Vettragarttā *grāma* containing the granted land.

3.4 Zone IV

The site of Anulia in the district of Nadia, on the other hand is located on Jalangi forming an extension of the Bhagirathi-Hooghly basin area. The zone is typically characterized by sediment characteristics of Deltaic plains forming estuarine sediments of middle Holocene.

3.4.1 Anulia Plate of the Time of Lakṣmaṇasena

The copperplate issued in the third year of the reign of Lakṣmaṇasena 'was discovered in the month of Bhadra 1898, in the village of Anulia, near Ranaghat, in the District of Nadia' (Maitra 1900: 61).

It records the donation of the Mātharaṇḍiyā *khaṇḍa-kṣetra* in the Vyāghrataṭi area of the Paṇḍravarddana bhukti with its four boundaries as the following:

the banyan tree as its boundary on the east, Jalapillā as its boundary on the south, Śāntigopī-śāsana as its boundary on the west and Malamañcha-vāṭi as its boundary on the north (Majumdar 1929: 90).

It is not surprising to note that epigraphists failed to precisely locate Mātharaṇḍiyā, for it was only a 'fragment of [arable] land' (i.e. *khaṇḍa-kṣetra*), yet to become a settled locality, during the time of issuance of the grant. It is quite likely that the locality changed its name soon after achieving the status of an *agrahāra* settlement having some concentration of Brāhmaṇ communities within its periphery.

3.5 Zone V

This zone to the extreme southwestern West Bengal is hydrographically controlled by the

current flow of the river Subarnarekha and the two epigraphic provenances of Antla and Panchrol in the two Medinipur districts are located more or less at the juncture of the *rarh* and the coastal tracts. Morphologically it represents an extended segment of the *Sijua* surface.

3.5.1 Antla ('Midnapore') Plates of the Time of Śaśāṅka

The noted 'Midnapore' plates were first reported and edited by Manishi Nath Basu (Basu 1938) and were subsequently edited by R. C. Majumdar (Majumdar 1945) and D. C. Sircar (Sircar 1943, 1982: 49-58, 1983: 24-7). R. C. Majumdar reports that the 'plates were secured by Mr B. R. Sen, ICS, collector of Midnapore, in August 1937, from an inhabitant of the district, but no details of their actual find place are known. Mr Sen presented the plates to the local Sāhitya Parishad,' (Majumdar 1945: 1). D. C. Sircar wrote: 'it is said that these two plates were secured from a Muslim resident of southern Medinipur...' (Sircar 1982: 49). Recently Pijush Kanti Sarkar has recovered that Manishi Nath Basu, who first identified the plates as belonging to the reign of Śaśāṅka, stated that the plates were collected from one Surat Khan of the village of Antla in the present Dantan Police Station of the district of West Medinipur (Sarkar 2006), but this information was not carried forward by later scholars.

These plates are dated in the ruling years of Śaśāṅka in the first half of seventh century and were issued from the *adhikaraṇa* stationed at Tāvira. The first plate dated in eighth year speaks of grant at a potters' village, viz. Kumbhārapadraka in Ketakapadrikā *uddeśa*⁶ in Daṇḍa *bhukti* by Śubhakīrtti, the governor of the province. The second plate dated in the nineteenth year records land grant in the Mahākumbhārapadraka village in Daṇḍa *bhukti* attached to Utkala-*deśa*.

R. C. Majumdar remarks:

[a]s regards localities mentioned in the inscriptions...Daṇḍabhukti and Utkala were

FIG. 5. Diagrammatic representation of boundary specifications of the Panchrol copperplate.

conterminous and the former comprised of the Midnapore district or at least the greater part of it...*Tāvira*, the administrative headquarters in Daṇḍabhukti, from which both the grants were issued, may be identified with Debra, about 15 miles south-east of Midnapore, and shown in Rennel's Map No. IX. The village Kumbhārapadrakā and *deśa* Kē takapadrakā I am unable to identify (Majumdar 1945: 2).

D. C. Sircar argues on the location of Daṇḍa *bhukti* that 'some believe that the modern name Dantan bears the memory of ancient *daṇḍa-bhukti*. However, the notion seems linguistically untenable' (Sircar 1982b: 51). It is interesting to note that a village named Kotpada still exists in the Dantan Police Station and not far

away from Antla, the actual provenance of the plate. Kotpada is in all probability the corrupt form of the name Kē takapadrakā.

3.5.2 Panchrol ('Egra') Plate of the Time of Śaśāṅka

More famous as the 'Egra' plate, this inscription actually hailed from a village called Panchrol in the Egra Police Station of the district of present West Medinipur (for the history of its notice, see Sircar 1982: 59, see also Sircar 1983: 727-30, 1986: 133-8). The plate is dated in the first half of the seventh century CE. It was issued from the *adhikaraṇa* of the Ekataḥakṣa *viṣaya*. It records land grant in the Kaparddipadrakā *grāma* in the Ekataḥakṣa *viṣaya*. A number of neighbouring rural localities and

their residents who figured at the office of the Ekatākakṣa *viśaya* during the proclamation of the grant are mentioned in the context of the complex procedures of the grant. These localities are Trāṇeka *agrahāra*, Taraktodarbhā *agrahāra*, Loḍḍāvā *agrahāra*, Ākhavaṭayika *agrahāra*, Viṃśatikhaḍḍāna, Mṛgāṭā, Gurjārapadraka, Kāpalāśaka, Saṣarpavāsini, Brāhmaṇapadraka. What is most interesting is the complicated representation of the boundary of the grant and its spatial connection with the contiguous settlement landmarks in the form of 'pillars' and water bodies (Fig. 5):

100 *dronavāpas* of rent-free land granted in the Kaparddipadraka *grāma* was bounded to southwestern corner by the pillar of the *Kaṅṭhikārikā garttā*. To the south (of this land) lies the southern pillar of the western bank of the tank named Tāla *Puṣkarinī*. To the northwest is the eastern pillar of the tank called Bahidakīya-Sṛṣṭodaka. To the north is located the boundary pillar of Bhaktisvāmī *maṇḍala*. To the east lies the pillar demarcating the southern bank of the tank named Cāṇḍāla *Puṣkarinī*. To the south (of that tank?) is the eastern pillar of the Vedamattasvāmī *maṇḍala*. To the west (of the granted land) lies the northwestern corner pillar of the tank called Śuṣka *Puṣkarinī*. To the south (of that tank) is the p 10th pillar of *Kaṅṭhikārikā garttā* (translated after Sircar 1982: 63).⁷

It is intriguing to note that none of the eleven rural localities mentioned in the inscription has so far been identified.

3.6 Zone VI

This zone may be conveniently equated with the Sundarban mass of landscape on fluviially active Deltaic plains where a number of rivers like Bhagirathi, Rupnarayan and their tributaries empty themselves in the Bay of Bengal, creating a number of estuarine channels at its mouth. The land surface with saline soil is formed on 'lower immature deltaic plain on late Holocene' to present day tidal and estuarine sediments of

the *Sunderban* surface. A set of four twelfth century copperplates hail from four find-spots like Govindapur, Barrackpur, Dighirpar, Bakultala, and Rakshashkali in this zone.

3.6.1 Govindapur Plate of the Time of Lakṣmaṇasena

N. G. Majumdar reports that the copperplate, dated in the second year of Lakṣmaṇasena's reign,

was discovered about ten years ago in the excavation of a tank in the village of Govindapur, in the district of 24 Parganas, near the Baruipur Station of the Diamond Harbour Branch of the E. B. Railway (Majumdar 1929: 92).

However, the plate was first noticed by Pandit A. C. Vidyabhushan, as Majumdar observes, and was deciphered by Vidyabhushan in 1925 in a contemporary Bengali periodical after its notice by R. D. Banerji in his *Banglar Itihas* in 1923 (Banerji 1998: 327, 335). The plate is dated in the second ruling year of Lakṣmaṇasena and it records the donation of certain amount of land in the Viḍḍāra *sāsana* in the Vetaḍḍa *caturaka* of Paścīma Khāṭikā within Varddhamāna *bhukti*. The granted land had the following boundaries:

To the east, the river Ganges, half boundary; to the south, the temple (*maṇḍapa*) of Leṅgadeva, another boundary; to the west, the orchard of Pomegranet, another boundary; to the north, Dharmanagara, another boundary... (Majumdar 1929: 93-4).

R. D. Banerji identified Vetaḍḍa *caturaka* with modern Betad in the district of Howrah (Banerji 1998: 335). All the later historians including N. G. Majumdar, the editor of the plate, unanimously accepted this identification without any question. It is only recently that the identification of this name has been rightly questioned on sound logical planks by Tapan Kumar Das. After a detailed field investigation coupled with a reconsideration of the boundary specifications gleaned from the Govindapur

plate, Das argues that Betadḍa *caturaka* is more logically identifiable with the site Betor in the Amta Polica Station of the district of Howrah rather than with its namesake in the Sibpur area of the same district (Das 2008). Controversy also prevails about the present location of the village Viḍḍāra, a *śāsana* category the village containing the granted land. Kalidas Dutta intended to identify the locality as early as 1933-4 with present Sasan village near the Baruipur railway station, altogether mistaking the technical expression *śāsana* (i.e. 'rent-free' village) as a segment of the proper noun Viḍḍāra (Dutta 1930, 1989: 90). T. K. Das has identified it with a village, within the Amta Police Station and not far from Betor, called Bidar. In terms of phonetic considerations the identification offered by Das seems apparently correct. But a crucial clue to its identification provided in the inscription that Das did not pay attention to was that the village Viḍḍāra was contiguous to Dharmmanagara, the latter forming the northern boundary of the former. N. G. Majumdar rightly noted this important piece of evidence and wrote:

Betadḍa-*caturaka* in which the village Viḍḍāraśāsana was situated, having the Ganges as its eastern boundary, is identifiable with modern Betad in Howrah district. It would be interesting to enquire whether near Betad there is at present any place answering to 'Dharmanagara', which is given as one of the boundaries of Viḍḍāraśāsana (Majumdar 1929: 94).

Now, within the present jurisdiction of the Police Station of Gobindapur there is a village called Biral (to be pronounced properly as Viḍḍāla), located about 2 km west of Padmapukur on the Baruipur-Amtala road and close to the actual provenance of the copperplate. Firstly, the name Biral (properly pronounced as Viḍḍāla) is a linguistically more justifiable corruption of the name Viḍḍāra than that of Bidar which has obvious phonetic similarity with Viḍḍāra, but cannot be linguistically clarified.

More importantly, the officially recorded name of the present village is Biral-Dhamnagar (22°22'12" N, 88°24'11" E), both being contiguous localities and the latter (i.e. Dhamnagar) undoubtedly bearing the vestige of its early medieval name. Finally, the Biral-Dhamnagar area is full of archaeological materials in the form of extensive surface scatters of pottery, brick remains exposed in the section of one of the tanks of the locality and occasional reports of sculptural materials testifying to its antiquity (Mandal 2002: 165-9). Thus, it will be more tenable to identify the Biral-Dhamnagar locality with the village granted through the Govindapur plate.

3.6.2 Barrackpur Plate of the Time of Vijayasena

The Barrackpur copperplate is the earliest epigraphic document of the Sena family from West Bengal. It was found at a village in the present Barrackpur Polica Station in the district of North 24 Parganas. The exact provenance of the record has however remained unknown as the editor of the plate records:

This copper-plate was discovered some eighteen years ago in a village near Barrackpur Cantonment in the district of 24 Parganas by Mr. G. A. Schumacher, as assistant in the service of Messrs. Bird & Co. of Calcutta. The circumstances under which it was found are not known. According to Mr. R. D. Banerji the plate after being for some time in the hands of the late Mr. V. Venkayya in 1910, was sent to the late Dr. D. B. Spooner, and ultimately in 1915 Mr. Banerji discovered that it had found its way to England, where it is now probably in the possession of Mr. Schumacher (Majumdar 1929: 57).

The plate was issued from the administrative headquarters of the Senas stationed at Vikramapura, like all other Sena inscriptions discovered from the West Bengal sector of the Delta⁸ around the middle of the twelfth century in the sixty-second year of Vijayasena's reign

(Basak 1921a, 1921b; Banerjee 1925). The inscription engraved on the plate records the donation of some lands in the Ghāśasambhoga Bhāṭṭavaḍā grāma, 'having half of the marshy land Tikshahaṇḍa as its southern, western and northern boundaries', in the Khāḍi viśaya of the Pauṇḍravarddhana bhukti. It may not be altogether unreasonable to identify Bhāṭṭavaḍā, though at the risk of doing so on sheer phonetic grounds, with present settlement at Bhatpara in the same region. The editor suggests that a 'Sambhoga is probably a territorial unit like bhāga which consisted of grāmas, e.g. in Dudia plates of Pravarasena II' (Majumdar 1929: 59).

3.6.3 Dighirpar-Bakultala ('Sundarban') Plate of the Time of Lakṣmaṇasena

N. G. Majumdar assumes that the copperplate was discovered around 1886, depending on Marshman's citation of the plate in his *History of Bengal* published in that year (Majumdar 1929: 169). But the plate was lost soon afterwards and consequently no concrete information about its 'actual find place' was available to the scholars. However, Majumdar referred to a crucial clue to the exact provenance of the record when he wrote

This copper-plate was discovered...in that portion of the Sundarbans which is now within the District of 24-Parganas... A writer in the Bengali Journal *Bharatavarsha*, 1332 B.S., p. 622 says that it was found by the late Babu Haridas Dutt, Zamindar of Majilpur in excavating a tank in the village of Bakultala to the south of Kasinagar in the Diamond Harbour subdivision of the 24 Parganas (Majumdar, p. 169 and footnote 1)

The 'writer' N. G. Majumdar alluded to was actually Kalidas Dutta who made the above notice in his Bengali essay on *Adi-Gangatirastha Sundarbaner Katha* and later specified the provenance of the plate as 'Lot no. 22 Bakultala' in his *Appendix to the Annual Report of the Varendra Research Society 1928-29* in the form of an article titled *Antiquities of Khari* (see Dutta 1989: 50-1 and Bose 1989 for

further details). In spite of this precise citation of the name, the confusion regarding the actual provenance of the plate prevailed, for at present there are as many as three villages of this name within 'the Diamond Harbour subdivision' only. To which Bakultala should one ascribe, then, the 'Sundarban' plate? Dutta provided some more important sidelights: firstly, he stated that it was Lot no. 22 and located south of Kasinagar; secondly, a canal named Citaḍi-khāta, mentioned in the inscription as one of the boundaries of the granted land, still bore the name Chitari khāl according to Dutta. In the light of the data provided by Dutta it is now possible to identify 'Bakultala' with the present village called Dighirpar-Bakultala in the Kultali Police Station of South 24 Parganas because not only this village is located to the south of Kasinagar, but the canal Chitari, as we shall shortly see, can still be located within the vicinity of both the provenance and the granted locality.

Issued in the second regnal year of Lakṣmaṇasena, the copperplate records the grant of land at Maṇḍala grāma in the Kāntallapura caturaka of Khāḍi maṇḍala within the Pauṇḍravarddhana bhukti. Except one natural landmark in the form of a canal, all the other boundaries of the grant terminated in already created agrahāra lands for a particular class of royal officers: 'to the east, the land granted to Śāntiyāgarika Prabhāsa; to the south, half of the Chitāḍi canal (Citaḍi-khāta); to the west, the eastern side of the land granted to Śāntiyāgarika Rāmadeva; to the north, the land of the Śāntiyāgarika Viṣṇupāṇi (?) Gaḍoli and Keśava Gaḍoli' (Majumdar 1929: 170).

Kalidas Dutta rightly observed that '[t]he southern boundary of the plot is given as Chitadikhata which can be easily identified with the chitadi-khal of the present settlement (Dutta 1989: 51). One can still find the Chitari canal as a branch of the Thakuran river flowing through the southeastern border of Kultali. Since it was located to the south of the granted village of Maṇḍala grāma, the locality should ideally be placed to the north of the spill particularly since the water body has kept, unusu-

ally, its earlier course unchanged. Quite interestingly, to the northwest of the present course of Chitari, there is an uninhabited place locally called Mandaler Lot (officially enlisted as Lot no. 120). One comes across huge quantity of pottery strewn over the surface in the locality and a structural mound in the sparsely forested area. Proper clearing of the jungle will enable one to access the spot to have a detailed study of the brick remains at the site, though its early medieval antiquity is hardly questionable.

3.6.4 *Rakshaskhali Plate of the Time of Dommānapāla*

Issued from the royal headquarters stationed at ŚrīDvārahaṭāka, the Rakshaskhali plate is datable to the end of the twelfth century and records donation of land at Dhāmahiṭhā in Pūrva Khāṭikā. B. C. Sen and D. P. Ghosh, the first editors of the plate, have left a thorough account of the site from where the plate was recovered:

The copper-plate in question was discovered, quite accidentally, during reclamation of land from the dense primitive forest in F Plot, West Sunderban, near the sea-coast of Bengal. The site which is situated in the isles of Rakshaskhali, not far from the mouth of the river Hughly, is bounded by the vast expanse of water called the Satamukhi river on the west and the comparatively smaller estuary Burirhat on the east. The copper-plate was discovered while digging one of the many earth mounds scattered over the ground, each containing a square brick chamber with an extraordinary brick wall, surrounded by another thinner wall at a little distance. The chambers are now roof-less, but the thickness of the walls indicates that formerly they supported one or more storeys. The presence, however, of a Buddhist monument, referred to in the inscriptions is significant. The historic importance of the forest land is not only attested by the remains of temples and stray sculptures in stone, but also by the existence, in the neighbourhood, of a village with the

significant name “Pathar-pratima”. It is also evident that this portion of Sunderban, now infested by wild beasts, was a flourishing centre of civilization, with the old course of the Ganges flourishing by, at least up to the time of the Muhammedan invasion (Sen and Ghosh 1943: 321).

R. K. Ghoshal added the following note regarding the location of Pūrvakhāṭikā:

[i]t is probable that the present river Hooghly formed the natural boundary between the two *khāṭikās*. Generally speaking Pūrvakhāṭikā seems to have covered the large part of the present Western Sunderbans area (Ghoshal 1956: 119-24).

Subsequently D. C. Sircar argued on the basis of evidence from a different spatio-temporal context that Dvārahaṭāka, the place of issuance of the plate, was located ‘on the mouth of the Bhāgirathī in the vicinity of the Gaṅgāsāgarasaṅgama’ (Sircar 1958b: 43, 1963: 99).

4. SUMMARY AND RESUME

To sum up, the work has been exercised firstly to systematically summarize the settlement data preserved in early medieval epigraphic records of West Bengal and then to relate the database with their counterparts on ground. The two most crucial items related to this genre of study are the proper research and recovery of locations of documents and reasonably justifiable identification of names of rural settlements recorded in these inscriptions. The complete inscriptional source material on the growth of rural settlements in West Bengal – as envisaged above – highlights the following points:

1. The study reveals that in many cases the exact provenances of inscriptions have remained improperly recorded and since the land donation affair described in these epigraphs mostly has a close spatial connection with the find-spot, it is a prerequisite to properly trace the provenances; this exercise provides a ready and precise geographical context for the study

of settlements with archaeological methodology. Thus, the exact find-spots of the so-called 'Midnapore', 'Mallia', and 'Sundarban' copperplates have been recovered during the present study. Further, in some cases the exact provenances are known, but they are represented in terms of comparatively broader geographical contexts. For example, the 'Egra' and the 'Jagajjibanpur' copperplates can be better named as 'Panchrol' and 'Tulabhita' plates respectively, based on their exact find-spots.

2. Partially connected to the above point is the issue of identification of settlements. Although mostly the identifications are based on phonetic resemblances in ancient and modern place-names, mostly these identifications can be justified either directly in the light of specific sets of epigraphic statements or that of the nature and distribution of archaeological artefacts in the concerned localities. Furthermore, the issues of provenance and identification are sometimes found to be compatible to each other. For example, the villages Kutigram, Ambha, and Bhabki could only be related to their early medieval counterparts after the recovery of the exact provenance of the plate at Maliadanga.

3. It is found that not only detailed studies of the inscriptional texts and subsequent exploratory surveys are important in the entire process, a thorough scrutiny of the existing literature pertaining to epigraphic studies in Bengal, both in the pan-Indian and the local vernacular traditions, is found to be rewarding in finding and locating epigraphic find-spots and early settlements.

This paper is primarily aimed at preparation of a detailed settlement database for an ongoing project on the archaeological study of early medieval settlements of West Bengal. The study clearly revealed that both the issues of provenance and identification have remained neglected in archaeological researches on the region, though the existing body of literature in the field is nevertheless voluminous. The main focus of the essay, therefore, was primarily on the recovery of epigraphic find-spots that pro-

vide, if properly plotted, a precise and essentially micro-regional spatial context in undertaking archaeological studies on regional early medieval settlements. Secondly, proper identifications of early settlements, many of which still retain elements of phonetic linkages with their ancient names in areas having long rural settlement history – in many cases in compatibility with the recovered provenances of inscriptions – further strengthen the geographical and chronological planks in understanding patterns of evolutionary changes in the settlements in different spatio-temporal contexts.

The six major geographical areas considered for the present study and the occurrence of inscriptions of specific time periods within these sub-regional brackets primarily tend to show two crucial aspects related to the patterning of rural settlements. Firstly, rural settlements are often found to be represented in terms of a number of contiguous localities; it is quite significant to note that in many cases the present landscape still retains the early landscape characters, as it is evident in the case of the Malla Sarul copperplate. Even when villages are mentioned in connection with their neighbouring natural landmarks such as prominent water bodies, the overwhelming continuity of the landscape character is hardly disturbed as it is in the case of the Tulabhita or the Dighirpar-Bakultala plates. The second point is the gradual increase in the number of occurrence of land grant charters in northern West Bengal and coastal uplands in the later part of the early medieval period, as compared to still earlier settlements growing in the central-western and southwestern parts of the region. Detailed micro-level case studies on the nature of early medieval settlements based on archaeological research methodology, with an inroad through epigraphic source material connected to the ground through proper identification, is expected to open new areas of research on both settlement archaeology as well as local and regional historical geography.

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NOTES

1. The earliest discovery of a copperplate inscription in Bengal, however, was from the present Bangladesh segment of the Delta. The noted Mainamati plate of Raṇavaṅkamalla Harikeladeva was discovered in 1803 from the village of Kotbari (Khan 2007) in the present Comilla district and was noticed by H. T. Colebrooke (Colebrooke 1807), followed by the notice, in 1833, of the Ramganj copperplate of the time of Īsvaraḡhoṣa and that of the time of Viśvarūpasena from 'Edilpur' in 1838 (Prinsep 1838).

2. As ready references to major mistakes in recovering the provenances, one may refer to Ayoub Khan's otherwise excellent work where the village Khalimpur, the find-spot of one of most important epigraphic records of the Pāla period from Bengal, has been placed in the Murshidabad district (Khan 2007: 12) and then in the Malda district (Khan 2007: 11), whereas the proper name of the district should be present Nawabganj (i.e. former Maldaha). B. M. Morrison also committed similar mistake when he referred to the find-spot of Jayanāga's copperplate at 'Mallia' in the 'Burdwan' district on the basis of Barnett's wrong information (Morrison 1970: 160).

3. In the light of recent discovery of three copperplates of one Gopāla, the son and successor of Śūrapāla I, the Gopāla of the Jajilpara plate has to be considered as Gopāla III, though at the time of initial publication of the copperplate he was referred to as Gopāla II. For relevant discussions, refer to G.

Bhattacharya and others (Bhattacharya 1994 = 2000: 441-54, 1996 = 2000: 459-60, Bhattacharya 2009, Furui 2008, 2009, Mukherjee 1997-98b).

4. D. C. Sircar takes *udraṅga* to mean 'the fixed tax', 'the land tax', 'the principal tax', or 'the tax on the permanent tenants'. He also refers to a case where some lands are donated to a certain benefaction after converting it into an *udraṅga* (i.e. *udraṅgikṛtya*) and refers further to the post called *audraṅgika* who acted as the collector of such tax (Sircar 1966: 349). M. Monier-Williams explains the term as 'a town' (Monier-Williams 2002: 191). Gouriswar Bhattacharya is 'not sure if we should follow M. Monier-Williams for the meaning of the term' as he thinks that the term 'town' is 'rather inappropriate' to stand for *udraṅga*, but he does not state his reasons (Bhattacharya 1997-99: 90). It is not known from the inscription if Nandadīrghikā was converted into an *udraṅga* before land was donated for the monastery located there. But the proper name Nandadīrghikā itself might throw some sidelight in explaining the word *udraṅga*. That the waterbody (i.e. Nandadīrghikā) must have formed a major landmark of the settlement locality around it is obvious, for both the locality as well as the monastery standing there were named after it. Its prolonged impact on the neighbouring landscape character is further reflected in the survival of the name Nanda dighi/Nadgarh bil, still located within the vicinity of the monastic site and the exact find-spot of the epigraph. Now, if one looks for the etymology of

the term *udraṅga*, it can be readily derived from the root word *udrin* meaning 'abounding in water' (Monier-Williams 2002: 191). Is it possible then that the locality around Nandadīrghikā was termed an *udraṅga* (meaning 'a locality abounding in water') because its identity as a settlement locale was based on a waterbody of the same name, particularly when its connection with the system of taxation is not clearly understandable from the epigraphic text?

5. S. C. Mukherjee's translation of the boundary specifications of Jagajjibanpur plate: 'on the east-the river Taṅgila; on the south the half way of the stream of the same flowing hear *Kubja-joṭikā*; on the east, *Nārāyaṇavāsīya* (the abode of a certain Nārāyaṇa, or the shrine of the God Nārāyaṇa?) lying near the middle of the embankment of *Kāsiggara*; on the west, the water-fall of *Golaṭi*, the ant-hill and the *aśvatthva* tree in Jambhavāsaka (mud house); on the western part of the Nandā-tank, at a little distance, the vilva tree, the Vijjaga embankment and *āmalaki* tree on the western part of the *Nandā* lake and up to the half-stream of the Tangila' (Mukherjee 1997-98a: 68).

6. R. C. Majumdar read the name as 'Ketakapadrikā' and its terminological suffix as *deśa* meaning 'country'. D. C. Sircar read the name of the

area containing the granted village first as Ketakapadrikā (Sircar 1982: 53) and then as Kecakapadrikā (Sircar 1983: 24).

7. Dr Ryosuke Furui has kindly allowed me to reproduce his own unpublished reading of the boundary specifications of the Egra plate. Dr Furui reads the concerned segment as: '(As for which direction?) a peg at the southwest corner of the ditch Kaṅṭikārikā. Then as for the south, a peg to the south of the western wider side (mahāpadaka) of Tāla lake. Then as for the northwest, a peg to the east at the water filled lake of Vahidaka. Then as for the north, a peg at the border of Bhaktisvāmī maṅḍala. Then as for the east, a peg at the southern wider side of the lake of Caṅḍāla. Then as for the south, a peg to the east at Vedamattasvāmī maṅḍala. Then as for the west, a peg at the northwest corner of the dried up lake. Then as for the south, until the mark 10 at the ditch Kaṅṭikārikā.'

8. Some inscriptions of the Senas, dated in the ruling period of the successors of Lakṣmaṇasena like Viśvarūpasena and Sūryasena and discovered from present Bangladesh, are known to have been issued from certain 'village' level headquarters like Phaspha-grāma and Dhāryyagārma. For a detailed discussion, refer Sanyal (Sanyal 2009).

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